

Home > News > [Visual Astronomy Display: February 2015](#)

Enter Keywords...

Archives

Select Month

Tags

ASTRONOMICAL PLATES

ASTRONOMY

ASTRONOMY THESIS COLLECTION

CFA BIBLIOGRAPHY

CFA HISTORY

CFA NEWS

CULTURAL ASTRONOMY SERIES

EVENTS

HISTORY

METADATA

METASAT

ORCID

PHAEDRA

UNIFIED ASTRONOMY THESAURUS

VISUAL ASTRONOMY DISPLAY

WOLBACH LIBRARY

ZOONIVERSE

NEWS

Visual Astronomy Display: February 2015

Katie Frey

Updated on August 24, 2022

[Leave a Comment](#)

Visual Astronomy Display for February 2015

Highlights...

- A summary of the **past, present, and future of Moon exploration** from the European Space Agency, who also share a vision for what Lunar exploration could be;
- The Russian Federal Space Agency posted two videos recently, one showing **what it would look like for the sun to be replaced by other stars**, and one showing how it would look for the planets of our solar system to replace the moon;
- NASA shared a couple videos on **what the January 27th Nor'easter looked like from space**;
- Radar data collected by NASA's Deep Space Network shows that **asteroid 2004 BL86, which passed Earth on Jan. 26, 2015, has a small "moon" that orbits it**, and;
- A video of the northern lights from Ronn Murray which also shows four sounding rockets sent up into the night sky by the University of Alasak, Fairbanks to **study the interaction of solar winds and Earth's atmosphere**.

Crazy Engineering: Ion Propulsion and the Dawn Mission

[Playlist Archive Suggestions, Comments, or Questions](#)

Author Recent Posts

Katie Frey

Assistant Head Librarian at [Center for Astrophysics | Harvard & Smithsonian](#)

Katie Frey leads the development of the Unified Astronomy Thesaurus, a community supported linked data vocabulary for sorting, filtering, and exploring astronomical literature, data sets, images, etc.

About Katie Frey

Katie Frey leads the development of the Unified Astronomy Thesaurus, a community supported linked data vocabulary for sorting, filtering, and exploring astronomical literature, data sets, images, etc.

CfA Bibliography for
January 2015

Joel H. Metcalf Biography
(Part 1)

Leave a Comment

Logged in as Hayley Curtis. [Edit your profile.](#) [Log out?](#) Required fields are marked *

Comment*

Post Comment